

Pathway Analysis Report

This report contains the pathway analysis results for the submitted sample ". Analysis was performed against Reactome version 83 on 03/02/2023. The web link to these results is:

<https://reactome.org/PathwayBrowser/#/ANALYSIS=MjAyMzAyMDMxOTExMDhfNTkwOQ%3D%3D>

Please keep in mind that analysis results are temporarily stored on our server. The storage period depends on usage of the service but is at least 7 days. As a result, please note that this URL is only valid for a limited time period and it might have expired.

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1. Introduction

Reactome is a curated database of pathways and reactions in human biology. Reactions can be considered as pathway 'steps'. Reactome defines a 'reaction' as any event in biology that changes the state of a biological molecule. Binding, activation, translocation, degradation and classical biochemical events involving a catalyst are all reactions. Information in the database is authored by expert biologists, entered and maintained by Reactome's team of curators and editorial staff. Reactome content frequently cross-references other resources e.g. NCBI, Ensembl, UniProt, KEGG (Gene and Compound), ChEBI, PubMed and GO. Orthologous reactions inferred from annotation for Homo sapiens are available for 17 non-human species including mouse, rat, chicken, puffer fish, worm, fly, yeast, rice, and Arabidopsis. Pathways are represented by simple diagrams following an SBGN-like format.

Reactome's annotated data describe reactions possible if all annotated proteins and small molecules were present and active simultaneously in a cell. By overlaying an experimental dataset on these annotations, a user can perform a pathway over-representation analysis. By overlaying quantitative expression data or time series, a user can visualize the extent of change in affected pathways and its progression. A binomial test is used to calculate the probability shown for each result, and the p-values are corrected for the multiple testing (Benjamini-Hochberg procedure) that arises from evaluating the submitted list of identifiers against every pathway.

To learn more about our Pathway Analysis, please have a look at our relevant publications:

Fabregat A, Sidiropoulos K, Garapati P, Gillespie M, Hausmann K, Haw R, ... D'Eustachio P (2016). The reactome pathway knowledgebase. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 44(D1), D481–D487. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkv1351>.

Fabregat A, Sidiropoulos K, Viteri G, Forner O, Marin-Garcia P, Arnau V, ... Hermjakob H (2017). Reactome pathway analysis: a high-performance in-memory approach. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 18.

2. Properties

- This is an **overrepresentation** analysis: A statistical (hypergeometric distribution) test that determines whether certain Reactome pathways are over-represented (enriched) in the submitted data. It answers the question 'Does my list contain more proteins for pathway X than would be expected by chance?' This test produces a probability score, which is corrected for false discovery rate using the Benjamini-Hochberg method. [↗](#)
- 13 out of 18 identifiers in the sample were found in Reactome, where 99 pathways were hit by at least one of them.
- All non-human identifiers have been converted to their human equivalent. [↗](#)
- This report is filtered to show only results for species 'Homo sapiens' and resource 'all resources'.
- The unique ID for this analysis (token) is MjAyMzAyMDMxOTExMDhfNTkwOQ%3D%3D. This ID is valid for at least 7 days in Reactome's server. Use it to access Reactome services with your data.

3. Genome-wide overview

This figure shows a genome-wide overview of the results of your pathway analysis. Reactome pathways are arranged in a hierarchy. The center of each of the circular "bursts" is the root of one top-level pathway, for example "DNA Repair". Each step away from the center represents the next level lower in the pathway hierarchy. The color code denotes over-representation of that pathway in your input dataset. Light grey signifies pathways which are not significantly over-represented.

4. Most significant pathways

The following table shows the 25 most relevant pathways sorted by p-value.

Pathway name	Entities				Reactions	
	found	ratio	p-value	FDR*	found	ratio
Gap junction assembly	2 / 41	0.003	0.001	0.069	4 / 16	0.001
Gap junction trafficking	2 / 52	0.003	0.002	0.069	4 / 20	0.001
Gap junction trafficking and regulation	2 / 57	0.004	0.003	0.069	4 / 24	0.002
Oligomerization of connexins into connexons	1 / 3	1.97e-04	0.004	0.069	2 / 3	2.12e-04
Transport of connexins along the secretory pathway	1 / 3	1.97e-04	0.004	0.069	1 / 2	1.41e-04
Gene and protein expression by JAK-STAT signaling after Interleukin-12 stimulation	2 / 73	0.005	0.005	0.069	1 / 36	0.003
Sensory processing of sound by inner hair cells of the cochlea	2 / 76	0.005	0.005	0.069	1 / 7	4.95e-04
Interleukin-12 signaling	2 / 84	0.006	0.006	0.07	1 / 56	0.004
Sensory processing of sound	2 / 87	0.006	0.006	0.07	2 / 13	9.19e-04
Interleukin-12 family signaling	2 / 96	0.006	0.008	0.071	1 / 114	0.008
Extracellular matrix organization	3 / 328	0.022	0.01	0.071	13 / 319	0.023
Defective CHST14 causes EDS, musculocontractural type	1 / 9	5.91e-04	0.012	0.071	1 / 1	7.07e-05
Defective CHST3 causes SEDCJD	1 / 9	5.91e-04	0.012	0.071	1 / 1	7.07e-05
RHOT1 GTPase cycle	1 / 9	5.91e-04	0.012	0.071	1 / 3	2.12e-04
Netrin mediated repulsion signals	1 / 10	6.56e-04	0.014	0.071	4 / 4	2.83e-04
Defective CHSY1 causes TPBS	1 / 10	6.56e-04	0.014	0.071	2 / 2	1.41e-04
CHL1 interactions	1 / 10	6.56e-04	0.014	0.071	1 / 5	3.53e-04
RHOT2 GTPase cycle	1 / 11	7.22e-04	0.015	0.071	1 / 3	2.12e-04
Regulation of commissural axon pathfinding by SLIT and ROBO	1 / 12	7.87e-04	0.016	0.071	2 / 5	3.53e-04
Miro GTPase Cycle	1 / 12	7.87e-04	0.016	0.071	2 / 6	4.24e-04
Dermatan sulfate biosynthesis	1 / 13	8.53e-04	0.018	0.071	4 / 4	2.83e-04
DSCAM interactions	1 / 15	9.84e-04	0.02	0.078	1 / 6	4.24e-04
Role of second messengers in netrin-1 signaling	1 / 16	0.001	0.022	0.078	2 / 4	2.83e-04
Advanced glycosylation endproduct receptor signaling	1 / 16	0.001	0.022	0.078	1 / 4	2.83e-04
Platelet Adhesion to exposed collagen	1 / 16	0.001	0.022	0.078	1 / 6	4.24e-04

* False Discovery Rate

5. Pathways details

For every pathway of the most significant pathways, we present its diagram, as well as a short summary, its bibliography and the list of inputs found in it.

1. Gap junction assembly (R-HSA-190861)

Cellular compartments: cytosol.

The assembly of gap junctions involves (1) synthesis of connexin polypeptides at endoplasmic reticulum membranes, (2) oligomerization into homomeric- and heteromeric gap junction connexons (hemi-channels), (3) passage through the Golgi stacks, (4) intracellular storage within Trans Golgi membranes, (5) trafficking along microtubules, (6) insertion of connexons into the plasma membrane, (7) lateral diffusion of connexons in the plasma membrane, (8) aggregation of individual gap junction channels into plaques, and (9) stabilization of peripheral microtubule plus-ends by binding to Cx43-based gap junctions (see Segretain and Falk, 2004.)

References

- Segretain D & Falk MM (2004). Regulation of connexin biosynthesis, assembly, gap junction formation, and removal. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1662, 3-21. [↗](#)
- Bruzzone R, White TW & Paul DL (1996). Connections with connexins: the molecular basis of direct intercellular signaling. *Eur J Biochem*, 238, 1-27. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2004-04-22	Edited	Joshi-Tope G

Date	Action	Author
2007-01-03	Authored	Gilleron J, Segretain D, Falk MM
2007-01-09	Created	Matthews L
2007-01-26	Edited	Matthews L
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJB1	P08034

Input	Ensembl Id
GJB1	ENST00000361726.6

2. Gap junction trafficking (R-HSA-190828)

Gap junctions are intercellular communication channels formed from Cx (connexin) protein subunits (see Segretain and Falk 2004 and Evans et al. 2006 for comprehensive reviews). Connexins are transported to the plasma membrane after oligomerizing into hexameric assemblies called hemichannels (CxHcs) or connexons. Connexons dock head-to-head in the extracellular space with opposing hexameric channels located in the plasma membranes of neighbouring cells. The double membrane channel or gap junction generated directly links the cytoplasms of interacting cells and facilitates the integration and co-ordination of cellular signalling, metabolism, secretion and contraction. In addition to their role in intercellular communication, connexon hemichannels coordinate the release of ATP, glutamate, NAD⁺ and prostaglandin E₂ from the cells. CxHcs open in response to various types of external changes, including mechanical, shear, ionic and ischaemic stress.

The trafficking of gap junctions involves (1) synthesis of connexin polypeptides at endoplasmic reticulum membranes, (2) oligomerization into homomeric- and heteromeric gap junction connexons (hemi-channels), (3) passage through the Golgi stacks, (4) intracellular storage within Trans Golgi membranes, (5) trafficking along microtubules, (6) insertion of connexons into the plasma membrane, (7) lateral diffusion of connexons in the plasma membrane, (8) aggregation of individual gap junction channels into plaques, (9) stabilization of peripheral microtubule plus-ends by binding to Cx43-based gap junctions, (10) internalization of the channel plaque leading to cytoplasmic annular junctions, and (11) complete degradation via lysosomal and proteasomal pathways (see Segretain and Falk 2004). Aspects of gap assembly are described here.

References

Segretain D & Falk MM (2004). Regulation of connexin biosynthesis, assembly, gap junction formation, and removal. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1662, 3-21. [↗](#)

Kasprzak L, Laird DW & Castillo M (1995). Gap junction turnover, intracellular trafficking, and phosphorylation of connexin43 in brefeldin A-treated rat mammary tumor cells. J Cell Biol, 131, 1193-203. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2007-01-03	Authored	Gilleron J, Segretain D, Falk MM
2007-01-07	Edited	Matthews L
2007-01-09	Created	Matthews L
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJB1	P08034

Input	Ensembl Id
GJB1	ENST00000361726.6

Date	Action	Author
2005-01-08	Created	Joshi-Tope G
2007-01-03	Authored	Gilleron J, Segretain D, Falk MM
2007-01-26	Edited	Matthews L
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJB1	P08034

Input	Ensembl Id
GJB1	ENST00000361726.6

4. Oligomerization of connexins into connexons (R-HSA-190704)

The mechanism of connexin assembly into connexons has been well characterized. Two different types of connexons can be formed. A connexon containing six identical connexin molecules is referred to as an homomeric connexon, while a connexon containing at least two different connexin molecules is referred to as an heteromeric connexon. The connexin molecules making up an heteromeric connexon appear to belong to only one subgroup (alpha or beta); heteromeric connexons containing both alpha and beta subunits have not yet been observed. Indeed, an intrinsic signal in four amino acid positions appears to confer different physicochemical characteristics to certain connexins in the alpha and beta groups (Lagr et al., 2003). These intrinsic signals are Cx specific, however (see Gemel et al., 2006). Therefore, additional yet unknown signals are required to regulate connexin compatibility and hetero-oligomerization.

The identification of the subcellular location at which gap junction assembly occurs has proven difficult. One explanation for this difficulty may be that the location of oligomerization for each connexon varies depending upon Cx type or cell type. Oligomerization has been observed after ER membrane insertion (Cx43, Cx32, Cx26) (Falk et al., 1997; Ahmad et al., 1999; Ahmad and Evans, 2002), in the ER-Golgi-intermediate compartment (ERGIC) (Cx32) (Diez et al. 1999) and inside the trans-Golgi network (Cx43) (Musil and Goodenough, 1993).

References

Goodenough DA & Musil LS (1993). Multisubunit assembly of an integral plasma membrane channel protein, gap junction connexin43, occurs after exit from the ER. *Cell*, 74, 1065-77. [↗](#)

Ahmad S, Diez JA & Evans WH (1999). Assembly of heteromeric connexons in guinea-pig liver en route to the Golgi apparatus, plasma membrane and gap junctions. *Eur J Biochem*, 262, 142-8. [↗](#)

Ahmad S, Diez JA, George CH & Evans WH (1999). Synthesis and assembly of connexins in vitro into homomeric and heteromeric functional gap junction hemichannels. *Biochem J*, 247-53. [↗](#)

Veenstra RD, Beyer EC, Lin X & Gemel J (2006). N-terminal residues in Cx43 and Cx40 determine physiological properties of gap junction channels, but do not influence heteromeric assembly with each other or with Cx26. *J Cell Sci*, 119, 2258-68. [↗](#)

Lagree V, Richard G, Brunschwig K, Lopez P, Falk MM & Gilula NB (2003). Specific amino-acid residues in the N-terminus and TM3 implicated in channel function and oligomerization compatibility of connexin43. *J Cell Sci*, 116, 3189-201. [↗](#)

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Date	Action	Author
2007-01-03	Authored	Gilleron J, Segretain D, Falk MM
2007-01-09	Created	Matthews L
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1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJB1	P08034

5. Transport of connexins along the secretory pathway (R-HSA-190827)

Cellular compartments: cytosol.

Connexins follow the classical secretory transport route from the ER to the plasma membrane: ER -> ERGIC -> Golgi -> TGN (Trans Golgi Network) -> PM (Plasma Membrane). All connexins assemble or oligomerize into hexameric connexons. The site of assembly varies and depends on Cx isoform, or cell type (see Koval et al., 2006).

Oligomerization of connexins has been observed during ER membrane insertion (Cx32), just after exit from the ER, in the ER-Golgi-intermediate compartment (Cx26) and inside the Trans-Golgi Network (Cx43) (Falk et al. 1997; Ahmad et al. 1999; Musil and Goodenough 1993; Diez et al. 1999).

References

- Koval M (2006). Pathways and control of connexin oligomerization. *Trends Cell Biol*, 16, 159-66. [↗](#)
- Goodenough DA & Musil LS (1993). Multisubunit assembly of an integral plasma membrane channel protein, gap junction connexin43, occurs after exit from the ER. *Cell*, 74, 1065-77. [↗](#)
- Ahmad S, Diez JA & Evans WH (1999). Assembly of heteromeric connexons in guinea-pig liver en route to the Golgi apparatus, plasma membrane and gap junctions. *Eur J Biochem*, 262, 142-8. [↗](#)
- Ahmad S, Diez JA, George CH & Evans WH (1999). Synthesis and assembly of connexins in vitro into homomeric and heteromeric functional gap junction hemichannels. *Biochem J*, 247-53. [↗](#)
- Kumar NM, Gilula NB, Falk MM & Buehler LK (1997). Cell-free synthesis and assembly of connexins into functional gap junction membrane channels. *EMBO J*, 16, 2703-16. [↗](#)

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Date	Action	Author
2007-01-03	Authored	Gilleron J, Segretain D, Falk MM
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1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
GJB1	P08034

Date	Action	Author
2018-08-31	Modified	Orlic-Milacic M

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
CAPZA1	P52907

Input	Ensembl Id
CAPZA1	ENSG00000116489

7. Sensory processing of sound by inner hair cells of the cochlea (R-HSA-9662360)

Inner hair cells (IHCs) of the cochlea transduce sound waves into an ionic (mainly potassium) current that leads to exocytosis of glutamate from the IHC and activation of postsynaptic type I afferent fibers of the radial ganglion (reviewed in Meyer and Moser 2010, Moser and Vogl 2016, Fettiplace 2017). IHCs have stereocilia on their apical surface that are arranged in rows of increasing height, a "staircase" arrangement. Stereocilia of different rows are connected by a tip link comprising a CDH23 dimer on the taller stereocilium bound to a PCDH15 dimer on the shorter stereocilium. PCDH15 interacts with LHFPL5, an auxiliary subunit of the mechanoelectrical transduction channel (MET channel, also called the mechanotransduction channel), which contains at least TMC1 (adults) or TMC2 (newborns), TMIE, and the auxiliary subunits LHFPL5 and CIB2 (reviewed in Fettiplace and Kim 2014, Fettiplace 2016).

Deflection of the stereocilia by sound waves creates tension on the tip link that increases the open probability of the MET channel, which then transports calcium and potassium ions from the scala media into the IHC, depolarizing the IHC (reviewed in Fettiplace 2017). The potassium channel KCNQ4 located in the neck region of the cell may also participate in depolarization. The depolarization of the IHC opens voltage-gated Cav1.3 channels (CACNA1D:CACA2D2:CACNB2) located in stripes near ribbon synapses on the basolateral surface of the IHC. The resulting localized influx of calcium ions activates exocytosis of glutamate into the synapse by an interaction between calcium and Otoferlin (OTOF) on glutamate-loaded vesicles in the IHC (reviewed in Wichmann 2015).

Ribbon synapses are characterized by a multiprotein complex, the ribbon, that contains at least BASSON, RIBEYE (an isoform of CTBP2), and PICCOLINO (a small isoform of PICCOLO) and appears to act to transiently tether vesicles near the synapse and thereby increase the pool of readily releasable vesicles (reviewed in Safieddine et al. 2012, Wichman and Moser 2015, Pangrsic and Vogl 2018, Moser et al. 2020).

ATP2B1 calcium channels, ATP2B2 calcium channels, KCNMA1:KCNMB1:LRRRC52 potassium channels, and basolateral KCNQ4 potassium channels transport cations out of the IHC and thereby act to repolarize the cell and limit the duration of the synaptic potentials (reviewed in Patuzzi 2011, Oak and Yi 2014).

References

Wichmann C (2015). Molecularly and structurally distinct synapses mediate reliable encoding and processing of auditory information. *Hear. Res.*, 330, 178-90. [↗](#)

Moser T & Vogl C (2016). New insights into cochlear sound encoding. *F1000Res*, 5. [↗](#)

Fettiplace R (2016). Is TMC1 the Hair Cell Mechanotransducer Channel?. *Biophys. J.*, 111, 3-9. [↗](#)

Oak MH & Yi E (2014). Voltage-gated K(+) channels contributing to temporal precision at the inner hair cell-auditory afferent nerve fiber synapses in the mammalian cochlea. *Arch. Pharm. Res.*, 37, 821-33. [↗](#)

Kim KX & Fettiplace R (2014). The physiology of mechano-electrical transduction channels in hearing. *Physiol. Rev.*, 94, 951-86. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2019-09-23	Edited	May B
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2019-09-23	Created	May B
2020-09-14	Reviewed	Furness DN
2020-12-12	Modified	May B

2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
CAPZA1	P52907	STRC	Q7RTU9

8. Interleukin-12 signaling (R-HSA-9020591)

Interleukin 12 (IL-12) is heterodimeric cytokine produced by dendritic cells, macrophages and neutrophils. It is encoded by the genes Interleukin-12 subunit alpha (IL12A) and Interleukin-12 subunit beta (IL12B), which encode a 35-kDa light chain (p35) and a 40-kDa heavy chain (p40), respectively. The active IL12 heterodimer is sometimes referred to as p70. The p35 component has homology to single-chain cytokines, while p40 is homologous to the extracellular domains of members of the haematopoietic cytokine-receptor family. The IL12 heterodimer therefore resembles a cytokine linked to a soluble receptor.

IL12 is involved in the differentiation of naive T cells into Th1 cells and sometimes known as T cell-stimulating factor. IL12 enhances the cytotoxic activity of Natural Killer cells and CD8+ cytotoxic T lymphocytes. IL12 also has anti-angiogenic activity, mediated by increased production of CXCL10 via interferon gamma.

The IL12 receptor is a heterodimer formed by Interleukin-12 receptor subunit beta-1 (IL12RB1) and Interleukin-12 receptor subunit beta-2 (IL12RB2), both of which have extensive homology to IL6ST (gp130), the signal transducing receptor subunit of the IL6-like cytokine superfamily. IL-12RB2 is considered to play the key role in IL12 function, in part because its expression on activated T cells is stimulated by cytokines that promote Th1 cell development and inhibited by those that promote Th2 cells development. In addition, IL12 binding leads to IL12RB2 tyrosine phosphorylation, which provides binding sites for the kinases Non-receptor tyrosine-protein kinase TYK2 and Tyrosine-protein kinase JAK2. These activate transcription factor proteins in the Signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT) family, particularly STAT4.

References

Morinobu A, Moriguchi M, O'Shea JJ & Watford WT (2003). The biology of IL-12: coordinating innate and adaptive immune responses. *Cytokine Growth Factor Rev.*, 14, 361-8. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2014-06-04	Authored	Jupe S
2016-01-28	Reviewed	Meldal BH
2017-05-12	Reviewed	van de Vosse E
2017-05-17	Authored	Duenas C
2017-09-07	Created	Duenas C

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Input	UniProt Id
CAPZA1	P52907

Input	Ensembl Id
CAPZA1	ENSG00000116489

9. Sensory processing of sound (R-HSA-9659379)

In mammals, sounds are processed in the cochlea, a spiral-shaped organ in the inner ear (reviewed in Basch et al. 2016, Fettiplace 2017, Koppl and Manley 2019). Low frequency sounds are sensed at the distal end (apex) of the cochlea; high frequency sounds are sensed at the proximal end (base) of the cochlea (reviewed in Dallos 1992, Manley 2018). Sound vibrations are transmitted from the eardrum through the three bones of the inner ear (malleus, incus, stapes) and the oval window of the cochlea to the fluids within the cochlea. Within the organ of Corti in the cochlea there are 3 rows of outer hair cells (OHCs) on the external side of the tunnel of Corti and 1 row of inner hair cells (IHCs) on the internal side (Spoendlin 1967). Each IHC synapses with approximately 20 afferent myelinated type I spiral ganglion neurons and functions as a sensory receptor to convert the energy of sound waves to secretion of glutamate neurotransmitter. Multiple OHCs synapse with each unmyelinated type II afferent neuron and OHCs are also synapsed with efferent medial olivocochlear fibers (Spoendlin 1967). The primary function of OHCs, however, is amplification of organ of Corti motions in response to sound (Ryan and Dallos 1975). Amplification is produced by changes in receptor-potential driven cell length caused by changes in the conformation of the unusual membrane protein prestin (SLC26A5, Zheng et al. 2000).

IHCs and OHCs sense the sonic vibrations by deflection of stereocilia on their apical surfaces (reviewed in Fettiplace et al. 2017, McPherson 2018). The stereocilia are arranged in rows of increasing height, with a stereocilium of one row connected to a stereocilium of another row by a tip link composed of a CDH23 dimer on the taller stereocilium joined at its N-termini to the N-termini of a PCDH15 dimer on the shorter stereocilium. CDH23 is connected to the cytoskeleton of the taller stereocilium via MYO7A (MyoVIIa), USH1C (Harmonin), and USH1G (Sans) (reviewed in Peng et al. 2011, Cosgrove and Zallochi 2014, Barr-Gillespie 2015, Fettiplace 2017, McGrath et al. 2017, Cunningham and Müller 2019, Ó Maoiléidigh and Ricci 2019, Velez-Ortega and Frolenkov 2019) while PCDH15 on the shorter stereocilium interacts with LHFPL5, an auxiliary subunit of the mechano-electrical transduction channel (MET channel, also known as the mechanotransduction channel), which contains at least TMC1 or TMC2, TMIE, and the auxiliary subunits LHFPL5 and CIB2 (reviewed in Fettiplace 2016, Qiu and Müller 2018, Corey et al. 2019). Deflection of stereocilia in the direction that increases tension on the tip link causes depolarization of the cell by increasing the open probability of the MET channel, which then transports calcium and potassium into the hair cell according to the gradient of those ions between the scala media (containing endolymph at 154 mM K⁺ and <1 mM Ca²⁺) at the apex of the cell and the scala tympani (containing perilymph at 7 mM K⁺) at the base (reviewed in Fettiplace and Kim 2014). Similarly, compression of the tip link by deflection of the stereocilia in the opposite direction decreases the open probability of the MET channel and causes hyperpolarization of the cell.

Depolarization of IHCs causes opening of voltage-gated calcium channels arrayed in stripes on the basolateral membrane close to ribbon synapses formed between the IHC and the afferent fiber of a myelinated type I spiral ganglion neuron. This results in a localized increase in cytosolic calcium ions which interact with Otoferlin (OTOF) on glutamate-containing synaptic vesicles at the ribbon structure to activate exocytosis of glutamate into the synapse formed with the afferent neuron (reviewed in Wichmann 2015, Pangrsic and Vogl 2018). Ribbon synapses are distinguished by electron-dense ribbon structures projecting from the presynaptic membrane into the cytosol and comprising at least BASSOON, RIBEYE (an isoform of CTBP2), and PICCOLINO (an isoform of PICCOLO). The ribbon structures appear to transiently bind synaptic vesicles and facilitate resupply of synaptic vesicles at active zones to refill the pool of readily releasable vesicles (reviewed in Moser et al. 2006, Moser et al. 2020).

In contrast with IHCs, OHCs mainly function in sound amplification by decreasing up to about 4% in length in response to depolarization caused by opening of the MET channel and increasing in length in response to hyperpolarization caused by channel closing, resulting in alternating compression and decompression between the reticular lamina and the basilar membrane. The changes in the length of the OHC are caused by very rapid (microseconds), voltage-sensitive changes in the conformation of the membrane protein prestin (SLC26A5). Stereociliary ATP2B2 (PMCA2) extrudes calcium ions and basally located KCNQ4 extrudes potassium ions to repolarize the OHC.

OHCs are synapsed with efferent cholinergic medial olivocochlear fibers (reviewed in Fritzsche and Elliott 2017, Fuchs and Lauer 2019). Acetylcholine released at the synapse binds an unusual, nicotine-antagonized, nicotinic receptor comprising CHRNA9 and CHRNA10. Upon binding acetylcholine, CHRNA9:CHRNA10 transports calcium ions into the OHC. The calcium activates SK2 potassium channels (KCNN2) and BK potassium channels (KCNMA1:KCNMB1) which extrude potassium ions, hyperpolarize the OHC, and inhibit activation of the OHC.

Loud sounds can cause a temporary threshold shift (temporary loss of hearing) caused by damage to stereocilia and synapses or permanent threshold shift (permanent loss of hearing) caused by damage or death of hair cells and neurons (reviewed in Kurabi et al. 2017).

References

Lysakowski A, Moser T & Brandt A (2006). Hair cell ribbon synapses. *Cell Tissue Res.*, 326, 347-59.

Fettiplace R (2016). Is TMC1 the Hair Cell Mechanotransducer Channel?. *Biophys. J.*, 111, 3-9.

Kim KX & Fettiplace R (2014). The physiology of mechano-electrical transduction channels in hearing. *Physiol. Rev.*, 94, 951-86.

Fettiplace R (2017). Hair Cell Transduction, Tuning, and Synaptic Transmission in the Mammalian Cochlea. *Compr Physiol*, 7, 1197-1227.

Zalocchi M & Cosgrove D (2014). Usher protein functions in hair cells and photoreceptors. *Int. J. Biochem. Cell Biol.*, 46, 80-9.

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
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2020-09-14	Reviewed	Furness DN
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2 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 2 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
CAPZA1	P52907	STRC	Q7RTU9

10. Interleukin-12 family signaling (R-HSA-447115)

Interleukin-12 (IL-12) is a heterodimer of interleukin-12 subunit alpha (IL12A, IL-12p35) and interleukin-12 subunit beta (IL12B, IL-12p40). It is a potent immunoregulatory cytokine involved in the generation of cell mediated immunity to intracellular pathogens. It is produced by antigen presenting cells, including dendritic cells, macrophages/monocytes, neutrophils and some B cells (D'Andrea et al. 1992, Kobayashi et al.1989, Heufler et al.1996). It enhances the cytotoxic activity of natural killer (NK) cells and cytotoxic T cells, stimulating proliferation of activated NK and T cells and induces production of interferon gamma (IFN gamma) by these cells (Stern et al. 1990). IL-12 also plays an important role in immunomodulation by promoting cell mediated immunity through induction of a class 1 T helper cell (Th1) immune response. IL-12 may contribute to immunopathological conditions such as rheumatoid arthritis (McIntyre et al. 1996).

The receptor for IL-12 is a heterodimer of IL-12Rbeta1 (IL12RB1) and IL-12Rbeta2 (IL12RB2), both highly homologous to Interleukin-6 receptor subunit beta (IL6ST, gp130). Each has an extracellular ligand binding domain, a transmembrane domain and a cytosolic domain containing box 1 and box 2 sequences that mediate binding of Janus family tyrosine kinases (JAKs). IL-12 binding is believed to bring about the heterodimerization and generation of a high affinity receptor complex capable of signal transduction. In this model, receptor dimerization leads to juxtaposition of the cytosolic domains and subsequent tyrosine phosphorylation and activation of JAK2 and TYK2. These activated kinases, in turn, tyrosine phosphorylate and activate several members of the signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT) family, mainly STAT4, while also STAT1, STAT3 and STAT5 have been reported to be activated (Bacon et al. 1995, Jacobson et al. 1995, Yu et al. 1996, Gollob et al.1995). The STATs translocate to the nucleus to activate transcription of several genes, including IFN gamma. The production of IFN gamma has a pleiotropic effect in the cell, stimulating production of molecules important to cell mediated immunity. In particular, IFN gamma stimulates production of more IL-12 and sets up a positive regulation loop between IL-12 signaling and IFN gamma (Chan et al. 1991). The importance of IL-12 for this loop is demonstrated by IL-12 and STAT4 knockout mice that are severely compromised in IFN-gamma production (Kaplan et al. 1996; Magram et al. 1996), as well as by patients with IL12B mutations that are severely compromised in IFN-gamma production (Altare et al.1998).

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Date	Action	Author
2009-11-20	Created	Jupe S
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Input	UniProt Id
CAPZA1	P52907

Input	Ensembl Id
CAPZA1	ENSG00000116489

11. Extracellular matrix organization (R-HSA-1474244)

The extracellular matrix is a component of all mammalian tissues, a network consisting largely of the fibrous proteins collagen, elastin and associated-microfibrils, fibronectin and laminins embedded in a viscoelastic gel of anionic proteoglycan polymers. It performs many functions in addition to its structural role; as a major component of the cellular microenvironment it influences cell behaviours such as proliferation, adhesion and migration, and regulates cell differentiation and death (Hynes 2009).

ECM composition is highly heterogeneous and dynamic, being constantly remodeled (Frantz et al. 2010) and modulated, largely by matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and growth factors that bind to the ECM influencing the synthesis, crosslinking and degradation of ECM components (Hynes 2009). ECM remodeling is involved in the regulation of cell differentiation processes such as the establishment and maintenance of stem cell niches, branching morphogenesis, angiogenesis, bone remodeling, and wound repair. Redundant mechanisms modulate the expression and function of ECM modifying enzymes. Abnormal ECM dynamics can lead to deregulated cell proliferation and invasion, failure of cell death, and loss of cell differentiation, resulting in congenital defects and pathological processes including tissue fibrosis and cancer.

Collagen is the most abundant fibrous protein within the ECM constituting up to 30% of total protein in multicellular animals. Collagen provides tensile strength. It associates with elastic fibres, composed of elastin and fibrillin microfibrils, which give tissues the ability to recover after stretching. Other ECM proteins such as fibronectin, laminins, and matricellular proteins participate as connectors or linking proteins (Daley et al. 2008).

Chondroitin sulfate, dermatan sulfate and keratan sulfate proteoglycans are structural components associated with collagen fibrils (Scott & Haigh 1985; Scott & Orford 1981), serving to tether the fibril to the surrounding matrix. Decorin belongs to the small leucine-rich repeat proteoglycan family (SLRPs) which also includes biglycan, fibromodulin, lumican and asporin. All appear to be involved in collagen fibril formation and matrix assembly (Ameye & Young 2002).

ECM proteins such as osteonectin (SPARC), osteopontin and thrombospondins -1 and -2, collectively referred to as matricellular proteins (reviewed in Mosher & Adams 2012) appear to modulate cell-matrix interactions. In general they induce de-adhesion, characterized by disruption of focal adhesions and a reorganization of actin stress fibers (Bornstein 2009). Thrombospondin (TS)-1 and -2 bind MMP2. The resulting complex is endocytosed by the low-density lipoprotein receptor-related protein (LRP), clearing MMP2 from the ECM (Yang et al. 2001).

Osteopontin (SPP1, bone sialoprotein-1) interacts with collagen and fibronectin (Mukherjee et al. 1995). It also contains several cell adhesive domains that interact with integrins and CD44.

Aggrecan is the predominant ECM proteoglycan in cartilage (Hardingham & Fosang 1992). Its relatives include versican, neurocan and brevican (Iozzo 1998). In articular cartilage the major non-fibrous macromolecules are aggrecan, hyaluronan and hyaluronan and proteoglycan link protein 1 (HAPLN1). The high negative charge density of these molecules leads to the binding of large amounts of water (Bruckner 2006). Hyaluronan is bound by several large proteoglycans proteoglycans belonging to the hyalectan family that form high-molecular weight aggregates (Roughley 2006), accounting for the turgid nature of cartilage.

The most significant enzymes in ECM remodeling are the Matrix Metalloproteinase (MMP) and A disintegrin and metalloproteinase with thrombospondin motifs (ADAMTS) families (Cawston & Young 2010). Other notable ECM degrading enzymes include plasmin and cathepsin G. Many ECM proteinases are initially present as precursors, activated by proteolytic processing. MMP precursors include an amino prodomain which masks the catalytic Zn-binding motif (Page-McCawet al. 2007). This can be removed by other proteinases, often other MMPs. ECM proteinases can be inactivated by degradation, or blocked by inhibitors. Some of these inhibitors, including alpha2-macroglobulin, alpha1-proteinase inhibitor, and alpha1-chymotrypsin can inhibit a large variety of proteinases (Woessner & Nagase 2000). The tissue inhibitors of metalloproteinases (TIMPs) are potent MMP inhibitors (Brew & Nagase 2010).

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2011-08-05	Created	Jupe S
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2013-05-22	Reviewed	Ricard-Blum S

Date	Action	Author
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

3 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 3 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
FBLN2	P98095	ITGA1	P56199	VCAN	P13611

12. Defective CHST14 causes EDS, musculocontractural type (R-HSA-3595174)

Diseases: Ehlers-Danlos syndrome.

Carbohydrate sulfotransferase 14 (CHST14 also known as D4ST-1) mediates the transfer of sulfate to position 4 of further N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) residues of dermatan sulfate (DS). Defects in CHST14 cause Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, musculocontractural type (MIM:601776). The Ehlers-Danlos syndromes (EDS) are a group of connective tissue disorders that share common features such as skin hyperextensibility, articular hypermobility and tissue fragility (Beighton et al. 1998). The musculocontractural form of EDS (MIM:601776) include distinctive characteristics such as craniofacial dysmorphism, congenital contractures of fingers and thumbs, clubfeet, severe kyphoscoliosis and muscular hypotonia (Malfait et al. 2010).

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Date	Action	Author
2013-05-21	Edited	Jassal B
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1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
VCAN	P13611

13. Defective CHST3 causes SEDCJD (R-HSA-3595172)

Diseases: spondyloepimetaphyseal dysplasia.

Carbohydrate sulfotransferase 3 (CHST3) transfers sulfate (SO₄²⁻) to position 6 of N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) residues of chondroitin-containing proteins resulting in chondroitin sulfate (CS), the predominant glycosaminoglycan present in cartilage. Defects in CHST3 result in spondyloepiphyseal dysplasia with congenital joint dislocations (SEDCJD; MIM:143095), a bone dysplasia clinically characterized by severe progressive kyphoscoliosis (abnormal curvature of the spine), arthritic changes with joint dislocations and short stature in adulthood (Unger et al. 2010).

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1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
VCAN	P13611

14. RHOT1 GTPase cycle (R-HSA-9013425)

This pathway catalogues guanine nucleotide exchange factors (GEFs) and effectors of RHOT1 (also known as MIRO-1). RHOT1 possesses a high intrinsic GTP-ase activity and does not require a GTPase activator protein (GAP) (Peters et al. 2018). No GDP dissociation inhibitors (GDIs) have been reported to interact with RHOT1. RHOT1 is a mitochondrial RHO GTPase. Like related RHOT2 (MIRO-2), RHOT1 localizes to the outer mitochondrial membrane. RHOT1 is implicated in mitochondrial movement inside the cells (Schwarz 2013), including the axonal transport of mitochondria in neurons (Saxton and Hollenbeck 2012; Birsa et al. 2013; Devine et al. 2016), as well as mitochondrial fission and fusion (Saxton and Hollenbeck 2012). RHOT1/RHOT2-mediated mitochondrial turnover is affected in neurodegenerative diseases (Birsa et al. 2013; Devine et al. 2016). RHOT1 can localize to peroxisomes and regulate peroxisome motility and fission (Castro et al. 2018, Okumoto et al. 2018, Covill-Cooke et al. 2020). RHOT1 is also involved in the regulation of ER-mitochondria membrane contact sites (Grossmann et al. 2019, Modi et al. 2019).

Upregulation of RHOT1 has a neuroprotective effect in ischemic stroke (Wei et al. 2019).

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2017-07-25	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
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2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
MYO19	Q96H55

15. Netrin mediated repulsion signals (R-HSA-418886)

Cellular compartments: plasma membrane.

Unc5 netrin receptors mediate repellent responses to netrin. Four Unc5 members have been found in humans: Unc5A, B, C and D. Different studies have suggested that long-range repulsion to netrin requires the cooperation of Unc5 and DCC, but that Unc5 without DCC is sufficient for short-range repulsion. The binding of netrin to Unc5 triggers the phosphorylation of Unc5 in its ZU-5 domain. Several proteins have been proposed to interact with Unc5 family members in mediating a repellent response, including tyrosine phosphatase Shp2, the F-actin anti-capping protein Mena, and ankyrin.

References

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2008-07-16	Authored	Garapati P V
2008-07-30	Edited	Garapati P V
2009-04-27	Created	Garapati P V
2010-02-16	Reviewed	Cooper HM
2010-05-20	Modified	Garapati P V

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
NTN1	O95631

16. Defective CHSY1 causes TPBS (R-HSA-3595177)

Diseases: brachydactyly.

Chondroitin sulfate synthases (CHSY) are involved in the synthesis of chondroitin sulfate, adding alternately glucuronate (GlcA) and N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) to the growing chondroitin polymer (Mizumoto et al. 2013). Defects in CHSY1 cause temtamya preaxial brachydactyly syndrome (TPBS; MIM:605282), a syndrome characterized by multiple congenital anomalies, mental retardation, sensorineural deafness, growth retardation and bilateral symmetric digital anomalies mainly in the form of preaxial brachydactyly (literally, shortness of fingers and toes) and hyperphalangism (Temtamy et al. 1998, Race et al. 2010, Tian et al. 2010).

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VCAN	P13611

17. CHL1 interactions (R-HSA-447041)

Cellular compartments: plasma membrane.

Close homolog of L1 (CHL1) is a member of the L1 family of cell adhesion molecules expressed by subpopulations of neurons and glia in the central and peripheral nervous system. CHL1 like L1 promotes neuron survival and neurite outgrowth. CHL1 shares the basic structural arrangement of L1 family members yet in contrast to all the members it is not capable of forming homophilic adhesion. The second Ig-like domain of CHL1 contains the integrin interaction motif RGD rather than with in the sixth Ig-like domain as in L1, however the sixth Ig-like domain of CHL1 has another potential integrin binding motif DGEA. CHL1 binds NP-1 via the Ig1 sequence FASNRL to mediate repulsive axon guidance to Sema3A. CHL1 is the only L1 family member with an altered sequence (FIGAY) in the ankyrin-binding domain, and it lacks the sorting/endocytosis RSLE motif, which is characteristic of other L1 family members.

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Input	UniProt Id
ITGA1	P56199

18. RHOT2 GTPase cycle (R-HSA-9013419)

This pathway catalogues guanine nucleotide exchange factors (GEFs) and effectors of RHOT2 (also known as MIRO-2). RHOT2 possesses a high intrinsic GTP-ase activity and does not require a GTPase activator protein (GAP) (Peters et al. 2018). No GDP dissociation inhibitors (GDIs) have been reported to interact with RHOT2. RHOT2 is a mitochondrial RHO GTPase. Like related RHOT1 (MIRO-1), RHOT2 localizes to the outer mitochondrial membrane. Similar to RHOT1, RHOT2 regulates mitochondrial movement by coupling mitochondria to kinesin and dynein motors that transport them along microtubules (Devine et al. 2016). RHOT2 is also localized to peroxisomes and it is involved in peroxisomal dynamics (Covill-Cooke et al. 2020).

References

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2017-07-25	Created	Orlic-Milacic M
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1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
MYO19	Q96H55

19. Regulation of commissural axon pathfinding by SLIT and ROBO (R-HSA-428542)

Commissural axons project to the floor plate, attracted by the interaction of their DCC receptors with Netrin-1 (NTN1) produced by floor plate cells (Dickson and Gilestro 2006) and radial glia (Dominici et al. 2017, Varadarajan et al. 2017). Once an axon enters the floor plate, it must be efficiently expelled on the contralateral side. A switch from attraction to repulsion allows commissural axons to enter and then leave the CNS midline. Based on studies in *Xenopus* neurons and by yeast two hybrid screens, it is observed that the attractive response of axons to netrins is silenced by activation of ROBO. SLIT bound ROBO binds to DCC, preventing it from transducing an attractive response to netrin. The sensitivity of axons to the repulsive action of SLIT does not only depend on repulsive SLIT receptors (ROBO1 and ROBO2), but is also influenced by expression of ROBO3, a SLIT receptor that suppresses the activity of ROBO1 and ROBO2. Upon crossing the midline, commissural axons downregulate expression of ROBO3 and increase expression of ROBO1/ROBO2 (reviewed by Dickson and Gilestro, 2006). Two transcript variants of ROBO3, ROBO3.1 and ROBO3.2 are considered to play different roles in midline crossing. ROBO3.1 is expressed in the pre-crossing and crossing commissural axons, while ROBO3.2, generated by alternative splicing, is expressed after midline crossing and thought to block midline re-crossing (Chen et al. 2008). In addition to SLITs, a secreted ligand NELL2 also acts as an axonal guidance cue that, by acting through ROBO3 receptors, helps to steer commissural axons to the midline. Both ROBO3.1 and ROBO3.2 can bind to a secreted ligand NELL2. Pre-crossing commissural axons, which express ROBO3.1, are repelled by NELL2. Post-crossing axons, which express ROBO3.2 are not repelled by NELL2 (Jaworski et al. 2015).

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2008-09-05	Edited	Garapati P V
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NTN1	O95631

20. Miro GTPase Cycle (R-HSA-9715370)

Miro GTPases are a separate family of Ras-related GTPases that are sometimes included in the atypical RHO GTPases group, but are phylogenetically distinct from the Rho family (Jaffe and Hall 2005; Boureux et al. 2007; Devine et al. 2016; Liu et al. 2017). Miro GTPases possess an additional GTPase domain more closely related to Rheb (Klosowiak et al. 2013). Miro family of RAS-like GTPases includes two members, RHOT1 and RHOT2. RHOT1 and RHOT2 regulate the movement of mitochondria (Schwarz 2013; Devine et al. 2016) and peroxisomes (Castro et al. 2018, Okumoto et al. 2018, Covill-Cooke et al. 2020).

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2021-02-05	Reviewed	Fort P
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MYO19	Q96H55

21. Dermatan sulfate biosynthesis (R-HSA-2022923)

Dermatan sulfate (DS) consists of N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) residues alternating in glycosidic linkages with glucuronic acid (GlcA) or iduronic acid (IdoA) residues. As with CS, GalNAc residues can be sulfated in CS chains but also the uronic acid

residues may be substituted with sulfate at the 2- and 4- positions. The steps below outline the synthesis of a simple DS chain (Silbert & Sugumaran 2002).

References

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2011-12-01	Edited	Jassal B
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Input	UniProt Id
VCAN	P13611

22. DSCAM interactions (R-HSA-376172)

Cellular compartments: plasma membrane.

DSCAM (Down syndrome cell adhesion molecule) is one of the members of the Ig superfamily CAMs with a domain architecture comprising 10 Ig domains, 6 fibronectin type III (FN) repeats, a single transmembrane and a C terminal cytoplasmic domain. DSCAM is implicated in Down syndrome (DS) due to the chromosomal location of the DSCAM gene, but no evidence supports a direct involvement of DSCAM with DS. It likely functions as a cell surface receptor mediating axon pathfinding. Besides these important implications, little is known about the physiological function or the molecular mechanism of DSCAM signal transduction in mammalian systems. A closely related DSCAM paralogue Down syndrome cell adhesion molecule-like protein 1 (DSCAML1) is present in humans. Both these proteins are involved in homophilic intercellular interactions.

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2008-09-05	Created	Garapati P V
2010-01-05	Edited	Garapati P V
2010-01-05	Authored	Garapati P V
2010-08-10	Reviewed	Clemens JC
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
NTN1	O95631

23. Role of second messengers in netrin-1 signaling (R-HSA-418890)

Cellular compartments: plasma membrane.

The levels of second messengers such as Ca²⁺, cAMP and cGMP may regulate the response of the growth cone to a particular cue. Netrin-1 as a guidance molecule depends on intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration, coactivation of PI3K and PLCgamma, and the type of response depends on the levels of cAMP.

Netrin first stimulates its receptor DCC, resulting in the activation of the enzyme phospholipase C. This then produces the messenger molecules, inositol-1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP3) and DAG, which in turn causes the release of Ca²⁺ from intracellular stores. Ca²⁺ release from the stores then activates TRPC channels on the cell surface. DAG activates TRPC3 and TRPC6 in a direct, membrane delimited manner, and IP3 may activate TRPC channels by depleting the ER Ca²⁺ levels.

References

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Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2009-04-27	Edited	Garapati P V
2009-04-27	Authored	Garapati P V
2009-04-27	Created	Garapati P V
2010-02-16	Reviewed	Cooper HM
2022-11-23	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
NTN1	O95631

24. Advanced glycosylation endproduct receptor signaling (R-HSA-879415)

Cellular compartments: plasma membrane, extracellular region.

Advanced Glycosylation End-product-specific Receptor (AGER) also known as Receptor for Advanced Glycation End-products (RAGE) is a multi-ligand membrane receptor belonging to the immunoglobulin superfamily. It is considered to be a Pattern Recognition Receptor (Liliensiek et al. 2004). It recognizes a large variety of modified proteins known as advanced glycation/glycosylation endproducts (AGEs), a heterogeneous group of structures that are generated by the Maillard reaction, a consequence of long-term incubation of proteins with glucose (Ikeda et al. 1996). Their accumulation is associated with diabetes, atherosclerosis, renal failure and ageing (Schmidt et al. 1999). The most prevalent class of AGE in vivo are N(6)-carboxymethyllysine (NECML) adducts (Kislinger et al. 1991). In addition to AGEs, AGER is a signal transduction receptor for amyloid-beta peptide (Ab) (Yan et al. 1996), mediating Ab neurotoxicity and promoting Ab influx into the brain. AGER also responds to the proinflammatory S100/calgranulins (Hofmann et al. 1999) and High mobility group protein B1 (HMGB1/Amphotericin/DEF), a protein linked to neurite outgrowth and cellular motility (Hori et al. 1995).

The major inflammatory pathway stimulated by AGER activation is NFkappaB. Though the signaling cascade is unclear, several pieces of experimental data suggest that activation of AGER leads to sustained activation and upregulation of NFkappaB, measured as NFkappaB translocation to the nucleus, and increased levels of de novo synthesized NFkappaB (Bierhaus et al. 2001). As this is clearly an indirect effect it is represented here as positive regulation of NFkappaB translocation to the nucleus. AGER can bind ERK1/2 and thereby activate the MAPK and JNK cascades (Bierhaus et al. 2005).

References

Humpert PM, Wendt T, Arnold B, Stern DM, Chavakis T, Bierhaus A, ... Nawroth PP (2005). Understanding RAGE, the receptor for advanced glycation end products. *J Mol Med*, 83, 876-86. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2010-06-01	Authored	Jupe S
2010-06-17	Created	Jupe S
2010-09-01	Edited	Jupe S
2010-11-09	Reviewed	Yan SD
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
CAPZA1	P52907

25. Platelet Adhesion to exposed collagen (R-HSA-75892)

Initiation of platelet adhesion is the first step in the formation of the platelet plug. Circulating platelets are arrested and subsequently activated by exposed collagen and vWF. It is not entirely clear which type of collagen is responsible for adhesion and activation; collagen types I and III are abundant in vascular epithelia but several other types including IV are present (Farndale 2006). Several collagen binding proteins are expressed on platelets, including integrin alpha2 beta1, GPVI, and GPIV. Integrin alpha2 beta1, known on leukocytes as VLA-2, is the major platelet collagen receptor (Kunicki et al. 1988). It requires Mg²⁺ to interact with collagen and may require initiation mediated by the activation of integrin alphaIIb beta3 (van de Walle 2007). Binding occurs via the alpha2 subunit I domain to a collagen motif with the sequence Gly-Phe-Hyp-Gly-Glu-Arg (Emsley 2000). Binding of collagen to alpha2 beta1 generates intracellular signals that contribute to platelet activation. These facilitate the engagement of the lower-affinity collagen receptor, GPVI (Keely 1996), the key receptor involved in collagen-induced platelet activation. The GPVI receptor is a complex of the GPVI protein with a dimer of Fc epsilon R1 gamma (FceRI gamma). The Src family kinases Fyn and Lyn constitutively associate with the GPVI:FceRI gamma complex in platelets and initiate platelet activation through phosphorylation of the immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motif (ITAM) in FceRI gamma, leading to binding and activation of the tyrosine kinase Syk. Downstream of Syk, a series of adapter molecules and effectors lead to platelet activation. vWF protein is a polymeric structure of variable size. It is secreted in two directions, by the endothelium basolaterally and into the bloodstream. Shear-induced aggregation is achieved when vWF binds via its A1 domain to GPIb (part of GPIb-IX-V), and via its A3 domain mediating collagen binding to the subendothelium. The interaction between vWF and GPIb is regulated by shear force; an increase in the shear stress results in a corresponding increase in the affinity of vWF for GPIb.

References

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- Moroi M, Miura Y, Takahashi T & Jung SM (2002). Analysis of the interaction of platelet collagen receptor glycoprotein VI (GPVI) with collagen. A dimeric form of GPVI, but not the monomeric form, shows affinity to fibrous collagen. *J Biol Chem*, 277, 46197-204. [↗](#)

Edit history

Date	Action	Author
2004-08-13	Authored	de Bono B
2004-09-25	Created	Farndale R, Pace NP, de Bono B
2022-11-19	Modified	Wright A

1 submitted entities found in this pathway, mapping to 1 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id
ITGA1	P56199

6. Identifiers found

Below is a list of the input identifiers that have been found or mapped to an equivalent element in Reactome, classified by resource.

13 of the submitted entities were found, mapping to 16 Reactome entities

Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id	Input	UniProt Id
CAPZA1	P52907	FBLN2	P98095	GJB1	P08034
ITGA1	P56199	KRT35	Q92764	KRTAP3-2	Q9BYR7
MYO19	Q96H55	NTN1	O95631	SH3RF1	Q7Z6J0
STRC	Q7RTU9	TBL3	Q12788	THBS4	P35443
VCAN	P13611				

Input	Ensembl Id	Input	Ensembl Id
CAPZA1	ENSG00000116489	GJB1	ENST00000361726.6

7. Identifiers not found

These 5 identifiers were not found neither mapped to any entity in Reactome.

8-Sep ACTR3B CTNND2 GOLGA6L6 MAGEA8